

How to Cite (APA): Gülbahar, S., et al. (2025). Prediction of yarn breakage probability in circular knitting machines: a baseline for industrial ai in textiles. In Proceedings of the IMSS'25 (pp. 401–408). Düzce University - Türkiye, 25–27 September 2025.

Prediction of Yarn Breakage Probability in Circular Knitting Machines: A Baseline for Industrial AI in Textiles

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KEYWORDS - Circular Knitting Machine, Yarn Breakage, Machine Learning, Predictive Maintenance.

ABSTRACT

Circular knitting technology is widely used in textile manufacturing due to its high efficiency and flexibility. Smooth and consistent yarn feeding is essential to maintaining continuous production. Yarn feeding systems play a critical role in reliably delivering yarn to the knitting mechanism, and their proper functioning is crucial for preventing yarn breakages. Such breakages not only disrupt production but also compromise fabric quality. Therefore, accurately predicting yarn breakage events is essential for implementing preventive maintenance strategies and enhancing overall production efficiency. In this study, machine learning methods were applied to estimate the probability of yarn breakages associated with the negative yarn feeding system in circular knitting machines. Operational data collected from these machines were used to train predictive models capable of estimating breakage probabilities. The results demonstrate that the machine learning model employed achieves high accuracy and consistency in predicting yarn breakage likelihood. The prediction model developed in this study lays the groundwork for applying AI-based solutions to enhance maintenance planning and production workflows in textile manufacturing, thereby contributing to smoother and more efficient operations.

1 INTRODUCTION

Yarn breakages are among the most common production issues encountered in circular knitting machines in the textile industry. These faults disrupt the production process and adversely affect fabric quality. A primary cause of yarn breakage is the malfunction of yarn feeding systems. Given the repetitive and high-speed nature of circular knitting operations, even brief interruptions can result in significant cumulative losses. Therefore, the ability to predict yarn breakages before they occur is critical for implementing preventive maintenance strategies and optimizing production efficiency.

In recent years, machine learning (ML) techniques have gained increasing attention in the manufacturing sector due to their ability to model complex, nonlinear relationships and identify patterns in large datasets [1]. Numerous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of ML in

predicting equipment faults, reducing unplanned downtime, and enhancing operational performance. For example, Azevedo et al. [2] employed AutoML frameworks and IoT-enabled data to predict yarn breakages in textile manufacturing, demonstrating the potential of explainable AI methods in minimizing machine stoppages. Kadam et al. [3] applied decision trees, random forests, XGBoost, and support vector machines (SVMs) to forecast failure durations in production lines, enabling timely interventions and increased productivity. Similarly, Saddala et al. [4] evaluated the performance of various ML models for predicting machine downtime, emphasizing not only their accuracy but also their interpretability. Montejano Leija et al. [5] further confirmed the utility of ML by showing how such methods can improve equipment reliability and fault detection in manufacturing environments.

Building on this foundation, the integration of ML-based predictive models into circular knitting operations presents a promising approach to reducing yarn breakages, improving fabric quality, and enhancing overall system efficiency. This study aims to compare various machine learning algorithms for predicting the probability of yarn breakages based on operational data collected from circular knitting machines.

2 METHODOLOGY

The primary objective of this study is to predict the probability of yarn breakages originating from the negative yarn feeding system used in circular knitting machines. Given the stochastic nature of breakage events and the relative independence of contributing parameters, a robust predictive framework is required. The methodological steps followed in this study are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Workflow of the research

The workflow begins with data collection and preparation, followed by exploratory data analysis to uncover inherent patterns in the dataset. Data preprocessing is then conducted, including handling missing values, encoding categorical variables, and applying feature scaling to ensure consistency across input features. Following preprocessing, feature selection techniques are employed to identify the most relevant variables that significantly influence model performance.

The refined dataset is partitioned into training, validation, and testing subsets to enable effective model development and unbiased performance evaluation. During the training phase, five machine learning algorithms—Logistic Regression, K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Random Forest, Extreme

Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), and Support Vector Classification (SVC)—are trained using the training dataset.

Model performance is evaluated on the test set using multiple classification metrics, including Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve (AUC), Precision, Recall, and F1-Score. These metrics collectively provide a comprehensive assessment of predictive accuracy and reliability. Finally, the results are analyzed to identify the best-performing models and to draw conclusions regarding their suitability for yarn breakage prediction in industrial circular knitting operations.

2.1 Dataset

This study was conducted in a textile facility specializing in the production of jacquard mattress fabrics. The factory operates continuously, 24 hours a day across three shifts, and houses a total of 87 circular knitting machines. Among them, Machine 2 was selected as the pilot system for analysis, as it exhibited the highest frequency of yarn breakages and the most frequent production stoppages. This machine was considered a representative case due to its operational relevance and diagnostic value.

A comparative analysis of short-stoppage distributions across all machines revealed a high degree of similarity. Since the machines are of comparable age, operate under identical environmental and operational conditions, and follow the same shift schedules, the findings derived from Machine 2 are considered generalizable to the broader production environment. Additionally, the low variability between shifts supports the assumption of consistent model performance across the factory floor.

The dataset comprises 2,565 samples and 11 features, sample of the data is given in Table 1. These features were selected based on their relevance to yarn breakage prediction. Key variables include product name, product weight (g/m²), number of stitch rows, raw material composition (%), machine speed (rpm), and fabric width (cm), among others. For model development, the dataset was partitioned into training (70%), validation (15%), and testing (15%) sets to ensure reliable model tuning and generalization.

Table 1 Sample Records from the Dataset Used for Yarn Breakage Prediction

Product Name	Product (g/m ²)	Stitch Rows	Raw Material Type (%)	Machine Speed (rpm)	Width (cm)	Machine Operator	Shift	Prod. Btwn Stops (m)	Prod. Btwn Stops (kg)	Type Change Status	Yarn Breakage Occurrence
CARBONO	220	9.9	0.941	18.5010	230	1	C	22.67	15.12	0	0
MIRACLE	230	10.8	0.96	19.0261	220	3	A	4.535	3.025	1	1
INTEL	400	11.7	0.81	19.0261	255	5	A	10.58	7.059	0	0
ANCELLICA	260	12.6	0.99	17.2306	230	2	C	33.76	22.52	0	1
GREYDARK	500	10.8	0.87	17.9692	220	1	B	16.12	10.75	1	1
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2.2 Data Feature Selection

A fundamental requirement for identifying and mitigating yarn breakages is a thorough understanding of machine operations and the analysis of relevant production data. Such analyses provide critical insights into machine behavior, performance patterns, and factors contributing to yarn breakages. The features considered for modeling, along with their descriptions, are presented in Table 2.

To improve data quality, preliminary preprocessing steps including imputation of missing values and correction of inconsistencies were conducted prior to feature selection. Feature selection was then performed using Sequential Feature Selection (SFS), a wrapper method that iteratively evaluates subsets of features based on their impact on model performance [6].

In this study, the forward selection variant of SFS was adopted. A k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN) classifier with k=3 was used as the base estimator, and performance was evaluated using 5-fold cross-validation to ensure robustness and minimize overfitting [7]. The average classification accuracy was plotted against the number of selected features, as shown in Figure 2, with the optimal subset

determined just before performance began to decline. This approach improves model generalization, reduces complexity, and minimizes computational cost by removing irrelevant or redundant features [8].

Table 2 Features and Descriptions

Feature	Description
Shift	The factory operates in three shifts: Shift A (11:00 PM–7:00 AM), Shift B (7:00 AM–3:00 PM), and Shift C (3:00 PM–11:00 PM).
Machine Operator	The operator responsible for overseeing machinery and ensuring continuous production.
Production Quantity Between Stoppages (m)	The amount of fabric produced (in meters) between consecutive production stoppages.
Production Quantity Between Stoppages (kg)	The mass of fabric produced (in kilograms) between production stoppages.
Type Change Status	Indicates whether a product type change occurred on a given day (1 = change, 0 = no change).
Machine Speed (rpm)	The rotation speed of the knitting cylinder in revolutions per minute.
Product Name	The specific product being manufactured during the stoppage.
Product Weight (g/m ²)	The weight per square meter of the produced fabric.
Stitch Rows	The number of stitch rows per centimeter.
Width (cm)	The fabric width in centimeters.
Raw Material Composite Index	A composite index representing the weighted average of polyester, viscose, and cotton ratios. This material index is calculated as: $\text{Material Index} = w_1 \cdot R_{polyester} + w_2 \cdot R_{viscose} + w_3 \cdot R_{cotton}$ where R_i represents the proportion of each fiber (summing to 1), and w_i denotes the corresponding weight assigned based on expert input regarding their influence on yarn strength and breakage risk.
Yarn Breakage Occurrence	The target variable: 1 indicates that a yarn breakage occurred during operation; 0 indicates no breakage.

Figure 2: SFS – Accuracy vs. Number of Selected Features

As a result of the SFS procedure, seven features were selected from the original eleven. These include product name, product weight (g/m²), number of stitch rows, raw material composition, machine speed (rpm), fabric width (cm), and machine operator, as illustrated in Figure 3.

2.3 Machine Learning Modeling and Analysis

This section presents the machine learning models used to predict yarn breakages, along with their configurations and performance evaluation. Five different classification algorithms were implemented in Python: Logistic Regression, k-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Random Forest, Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), and Support Vector Classification (SVC). Brief explanations of the algorithms are given below:

Logistic Regression is a widely used statistical model that estimates class probabilities using a sigmoid function applied to a linear combination of input features. Model parameters were optimized

via maximum likelihood estimation [9]. In this study, the model was trained using the 'lbfgs' solver with a maximum of 200 iterations.

Figure 3: Features Selected with the Sequential Feature Selection Method

K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) is a non-parametric method that classifies new observations based on the majority class among their k nearest neighbors using Euclidean distance [10]. K was set to 5 in this study.

Random Forest is an ensemble learning method that builds multiple decision trees using random subsets of the data and features. Final predictions are made through majority voting, which improves robustness and mitigates overfitting [11]. The number of trees was set to 100.

XGBoost is a gradient boosting framework that sequentially builds decision trees, each attempting to correct the errors of its predecessor [12]. The model was configured to optimize classification accuracy using the logloss evaluation metric, with label encoding disabled to improve learning stability in the presence of categorical or noisy data.

Support Vector Classification (SVC) constructs an optimal hyperplane to separate classes by maximizing the margin between them. For non-linearly separable data, SVC employs kernel transformations to project inputs into higher dimensions [13]. Probability estimates were enabled for interpretability, and default settings were used for consistency.

Table 3 presents the performance metrics of five machine learning models used to predict yarn breakages in circular knitting machines. The models were evaluated using four key classification metrics: Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F1-Score.

Table 3 Model Performance Metrics

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Logistic Regression	0.826	0.867	0.926	0.896
K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN)	0.990	0.997	0.990	0.994
Random Forest	0.979	0.987	0.987	0.987
Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost)	0.982	0.990	0.987	0.989
Support Vector Classifier (SVC)	0.979	0.978	0.997	0.987

Among the evaluated models, KNN achieved the best performance with 99.0% accuracy, showing its effectiveness in capturing patterns related to yarn breakages. Following closely, XGBoost and random forest models also showed strong results with accuracies of 98.2% and 97.9%, respectively. These ensemble methods benefit from combining multiple decision trees, which enhances their robustness and generalization performance, especially in complex or noisy datasets. Their competitive accuracy values highlight their suitability for yarn breakage prediction as well. SVC also performed well with 97.9% accuracy, offering a strong balance between precision and recall. Logistic regression, while less accurate at 82.6%, provides a simpler and more interpretable

model that can serve as a baseline. These accuracy comparisons are visually illustrated in Figure 4, clearly demonstrating the performance of each model.

Figure 4: Accuracy Comparison of Machine Learning Models

In addition to numerical performance metrics, visual tools such as confusion matrices and ROC (Receiver Operating Characteristic) curves were employed to evaluate classification effectiveness.

Figure 5 displays the confusion matrix for the best-performing model, KNN, which achieved a classification accuracy of 99.0%.

Figure 5: Confusion matrix for KNN classification

Figure 6 presents the ROC curves of the five models for the test data set. The Area Under the Curve (AUC) values indicate the discriminative ability of each model. The closer the ROC curve follows the top-left border, the more accurate the model. XGBoost achieved a perfect AUC (Area Under the Curve) score of 1.00, indicating excellent class separation. KNN, Random Forest, and SVC also performed strongly, with AUC values of 0.99. Logistic Regression recorded a lower, but still reasonable, AUC of 0.91. These results suggest that ensemble and distance-based models are particularly well-suited to this classification task.

Figure 6: ROC curves of the Classification Models

Although XGBoost demonstrated perfect AUC performance, the KNN model was ultimately considered the most consistent and practical choice, balancing high accuracy with strong performance across all other metrics. It proved especially effective in correctly classifying both positive (breakage) and negative (no-breakage) cases, making it a robust solution for real-time yarn breakage prediction in circular knitting operations.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The evaluation results indicate that both the KNN and XGBoost models achieved strong and reliable performance in predicting yarn breakages caused by negative yarn feeding in circular knitting machines. Among the tested models, KNN exhibited the highest classification accuracy (99.0%) with a relatively simple, interpretable structure, making it a practical choice for deployment in industrial settings. XGBoost, on the other hand, demonstrated excellent performance in terms of the AUC (1.00), showing its effectiveness in capturing complex, nonlinear patterns in the dataset.

Both models significantly outperformed the logistic regression baseline, highlighting the advantages of non-linear and ensemble methods in modeling production-related faults. The use of precision, recall, and F1-score as complementary metrics confirmed that KNN and XGBoost maintained high sensitivity and specificity across class distributions, ensuring balanced performance even under potential class imbalance.

This study differs from previous research by focusing specifically on yarn breakages caused by negative yarn feeding, using real operational data from textile manufacturing. It combines high predictive accuracy with interpretability, offering a practical and scalable solution for industrial settings.

The adoption of a machine learning-based approach for yarn breakage prediction has the potential to enhance operational efficiency by enabling timely detection and proactive interventions. Reducing unplanned machine stoppages contributes to improved fabric quality, reduced waste, and more efficient resource utilization in textile manufacturing.

Looking forward, the proposed models could be embedded into real-time monitoring systems within the production environment, enabling automatic alert generation and supporting preventive maintenance strategies. Incorporating operator feedback may enable the use of semi-supervised or active learning methods, allowing the system to adapt continuously to new patterns and edge cases. Additionally, the integration of sensor-based data such as tension, vibration, or ambient environmental conditions could further improve model sensitivity to early-stage faults.

Future research may also explore the use of reinforcement learning to move beyond prediction and toward learning optimal decision policies, aimed at minimizing downtime and optimizing machine utilization. Lastly, the development of risk assessment frameworks for yarn breakages across different machine types or production lines would provide valuable support for maintenance planning and resource allocation at the factory level.

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